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EFFECTS OF CAROB FLOUR AND SUGAR BEET FIBERS ADDITION ON QUALITY OF GINGERBREAD TYPE BISCUITS

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ABSTRACT

In many countries, production of gingerbreads has a long tradition. Gingerbread is a sweet bakery product that can take form of a cake or softer cookie. The formula for gingerbread dough may vary depending on local customs. Generally, it comprises wheat flour, honey, sugar, condiments and chemical leavens. In order to investigate the possibility of using carob flour and sugar beet fibers in formulation of improved gingerbread type biscuits, supplementation of part of the wheat flour with mentioned functional materials was carried out. Experiments were planned according to factorial plan 3², independent variables being carob flour and sugar beet fibers in amounts of 10%, 20% and 3%, 6%, respectively.

Quality of utilized gingerbread type biscuits was evaluated through examination of total polyphenolic content, antioxidant activity, pH and sensory parameters. Moreover, microbiological quality of products was determined by mesophilic bacteria, yeasts and fungi count after 2 months of storage.

Obtained results showed that the increase of carob flour in biscuits formulation increases antioxidant activity as well as polyphenolic content, while the introduction of sugar beet fibres does not significantly affect parameters mentioned. Sensory analysis showed increased firmness and unpleasant aftertaste in samples with high share of sugar beet fibers. On the other hand, addition of carob flour positively affected colour, aroma and sweetness of biscuits. In terms of overall acceptability, sample with 20% of carob flour obtained the highest score (higher than control sample). Lastly, fortification of gingerbread type biscuits did not affect the microbiological parameters.

Keywords: *gingerbread biscuit, carob flour, sugar beet fibers, antioxidant activity, quality*

INTRODUCTION

Carob (*Ceratonia siliqua* L.) pod represents a by-product of carob processing and has a high nutritive value. Carob pod contains 40-55% sugars, from which are dominant sucrose, fructose and glucose (Ayaz et al., 2007). Also, carob pod is characterized by higher content of dietary fibers (30-40%) and they consist of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and galactomannans (Haber, 2002). Furthermore, composition of carob pod is unique due to presence of high amounts of polyphenols (Saura-Calixto, 1988). So far, 24 individual polyphenolic compounds were identified in carob (Owen et al., 2003). Considering the combination of mentioned functional compounds and sweet taste, carob pod flour can be a useful raw material for the production of enriched confectionary food products, such as gingerbread type biscuits.

Gingerbread biscuits are products with a long tradition. They are a popular type of soft biscuits containing honey and spices. Traditional recipes for gingerbreads vary across Europe depending on the formulation, type and quantity of ingredients and applied technology (Filipčev, et al., 2011). The very important feature of gingerbread biscuits is that they belong to the category of bakery products with long shelf-life stability (Zielinski et al., 2012) and can remain fresh and flavorful for a long period of time. Their soft texture, sweet and pleasant taste makes them very favorable and attractive, especially for younger population. However, in their original recipes, gingerbread type biscuits are deficient in dietary fibers. This can be corrected by introducing a raw material rich in dietary fibers, such as sugar beet fibers. Sugar beet pulp as a fibrous by-product obtained from sugar production

is an important source of dietary fiber with fiber content more than 75% (approximately one-third of cellulose, hemicellulose and pectin) (Dinand et al., 1999). Preferable soluble/insoluble dietary fiber ratio, high water binding/holding capacity and low level of phytate make sugar beet fibers more attractive than cereal bran originating fibers (Šoronja-Simović et al., 2016). Addition of dietary fibers in food products enhances nutritional and reduces energy value of the product and can lead to increase of dietary fiber daily intake (Kritchevsky, 2001). In this respect sugar beet fibers represent rich industrial by-products with great potential for formulation of new food products.

As far as authors are aware, there is no literature data concerning the enrichment of gingerbread biscuits with carob flour or sugar beet fibers. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of carob flour and sugar beet fibers on functional characteristics of fortified gingerbread type biscuits: polyphenolic content and antioxidant activity. Also the sensory quality, as well as microbiological stability during storage of utilized gingerbread biscuits will be evaluated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samples were prepared from ingredients purchased from local suppliers: commercial wheat flour type 500, carob pulp flour, honey, vegetable fat, sugar, NaHCO₃, NH₄HCO₃ and lecithin. Sugar beet fibers were prepared according to procedure described by Šoronja-Simović et al. (2010).

The biscuits were prepared according to a two-phase procedure. Carob flour (C) and sugar beet fibers (F) were added as a substitution of part of wheat flour, and the amounts are shown in Table 1. Addition of all ingredients was calculated on flour weight. In the first phase, a mixture of honey (45%), sugar (25%) and lecithin (1%) was heated to 80°C. Homogenous mass was then added to 70% of total amount of flour blends. Water was added in amount to produce dough with 25% moisture and mixed with kitchen mixer for 10 minutes. Dough samples were left to rest over night at room temperature. In the second phase, honey dough was mixed with the rest of flour blends (30%), vegetable fat (3%) and a combination of NaHCO₃ + NH₄HCO₃ (0.5% + 0.5%). Obtained dough samples were covered with a plastic foil and left to rest at 8°C for 1 hour. After that, the dough was rolled on a pastry board to uniform thickness of 10 mm and cut into 5 cm diameter rounds. Biscuits were baked at 180°C for 17–20 min.

Table 1. The content of carob flour and sugar beet fibers in gingerbread cookie samples.

Sample	Carob flour (%)	Sugarbeet fibers (%)
K	0	0
C ₁₀	10	0
C ₂₀	20	0
F ₃	0	3
C ₁₀ F ₃	10	3
C ₂₀ F ₃	20	3
F ₆	0	6
C ₁₀ F ₆	10	6
C ₂₀ F ₆	20	6

Total polyphenolic content in obtained gingerbread biscuits was determined by Folin–Ciocalteu procedure using gallic acid as a standard (Granato et al., 2016). Absorbance was measured at 765 nm. Content of phenolic compounds was expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalent (GAE) per g of gingerbread sample (mg GAE/g). All experiments were performed in three replicates.

Antioxidant activity of examined gingerbreads was determined by Photochem (Analytic Jena AG, Germany) and using ascorbic acid as a standard. Antioxidant capacity of water-soluble antioxidants present in gingerbread cookies was expressed as nmol ascorbic acid equivalent (AAE) per g of gingerbread (nmol AAE/g).

pH value of samples was determined by standard procedure using glass electrode (Pravilnik, 1987).

In order to evaluate differences between cookie formulations, sensory assessment was performed. It was conducted by a group of 6 semi-trained panellists who were familiar with sensory analysis techniques (Resurrecion, 2008). The panellists were asked to evaluate each cookie attribute applying a hedonic scale of 7 points (1 — dislike very much, 7 — like very much). The following attributes were examined: color, firmness, taste/aroma, sweetness and overall acceptability. The sensory analysis was carried out 24 h after baking.

Gingerbread microbiological stability of gingerbread samples were evaluated through determination of mesophilic bacteria on plate count agar (PCA; Biolife, Milano, Italy) incubated at 30 °C 3 days (ISO, 2013) and yeast and fungi on dichloran rose-bengal chloramphenicol agar (DRBC; Biolife, Milano, Italy) incubated at 25 °C 5 days (ISO, 1987) after two months of storage.

Statistical method of analysis of variance (ANOVA) with *post hoc* Dunnett t test (IBM SPSS Statistics V23, IBM Corporation, USA) was used in order to determine the significance level of input factor to corresponding responses. A factor was considered to affect the response if the p-value is less than 0.05 (95% level of significance was used).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quality of gingerbread type biscuits is dependent on the ingredients used for their production. Introduction of new, functional raw materials – carob flour and sugar beet fibers – in preparation of gingerbreads can improve functionality of such products. Total polyphenolic content and antioxidant activity of fortified gingerbread biscuits are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of total polyphenolic content and antioxidant activity of gingerbread samples.

Sample	Total polyphenols (mg GAE/g)	Antioxidant activity (nmol AAE/g)
K	1.90 ± 0.11	122.40 ± 11.05
C ₁₀	2.79 ± 0.07*	234.70 ± 17.86*
C ₂₀	2.90 ± 0.11*	288.28 ± 45.06*
F ₃	1.70 ± 0.13	94.84 ± 15.19
C ₁₀ F ₃	2.25 ± 0.10	201.64 ± 57.83
C ₂₀ F ₃	2.91 ± 0.09*	218.16 ± 28.91*
F ₆	1.68 ± 0.04	85.03 ± 1.51*
C ₁₀ F ₆	2.25 ± 0.10*	196.19 ± 74.39
C ₂₀ F ₆	2.91 ± 0.20*	241.53 ± 28.90*

Asterisk (*) means significant difference compared to control ($p < 0.05$).

GAE – gallic acid equivalent; AAE – ascorbic acid equivalent.

It can be seen that the addition of carob flour to gingerbread formula significantly increased total polyphenols and antioxidant activity in comparison to control sample. On the other hand, sugar beet fibers did not majorly influence total polyphenolic content in gingerbread biscuits, but did significantly decreased their antioxidant activity (Table 2). This is with accordance with the study of Sakač et al. (2011), where the same effect occurred in cookies supplemented with sugar beet fibers.

The results shown in Table 3 indicate that the addition of carob flour and sugar beet fibers did not have significant effect on microbiological parameters after 2 months of storage in comparison to control sample.

Table 3: Results for pH, mesophilic count, yeast count and mould count after 2 months of storage.

Sample	pH	Mesophilic count (log cfu/g)	Yeast count (log cfu/g)	Mould count (log cfu/g)
K	6.28 ± 0.08	4.74 ± 0.55	3.74 ± 0.37	<10
C ₁₀	6.10 ± 0.01	4.79 ± 0.11	3.66 ± 0.26	<10
C ₂₀	6.27 ± 0.06	4.84 ± 0.36	3.89 ± 0.16	<10
F ₃	6.23 ± 0.11	5.10 ± 0.28	4.02 ± 0.03	<10
C ₁₀ F ₃	6.19 ± 0.04	5.07 ± 0.17	3.78 ± 0.43	<10
C ₂₀ F ₃	5.88 ± 0.17*	4.63 ± 0.44	3.60 ± 0.00	<10
F ₆	6.18 ± 0.03	5.00 ± 0.24	4.24 ± 0.09	<10
C ₁₀ F ₆	6.09 ± 0.10	4.83 ± 0.42	4.08 ± 0.05	<10
C ₂₀ F ₆	6.00 ± 0.04	4.72 ± 0.51	3.90 ± 0.08	<10

Asterisk (*) means significant difference compared to control ($p < 0.05$).

These results were expected and can be used as a confirmation that gingerbreads represent products with high sustainability. High share of sugar and honey in gingerbread biscuits composition along with low moisture content contributes to these facts. Moreover, fortification of biscuits generally did not affect pH value. pH value was slightly decreased exclusively in sample containing 20% of carob flour and 3% of sugar beet fibers.

Figure 1. Effects of carob flour and sugar beet fibers on sensory characteristics of gingerbreads.

Results obtained for the sensory attributes of tested biscuits (Figure 1) indicate that the addition of carob flour affected all quality parameters. The addition of carob flour for utilization of gingerbreads had major impact on the color of biscuits, changing it from light to dark brown (Figure 2).

However, the color change did not negatively affect the number of points for this parameter. Improvement was evident also in taste/aroma, sweetness and most of all overall acceptability of biscuits, with minimum negative effect on firmness of the product. On the other hand, the use of sugar beet fibers in gingerbread production did not affect the biscuit color, but did significantly increase firmness, and had changed taste/aroma of the product (with unpleasant

aftertaste). Negative effect of sugar beet fibers on sensory parameter mentioned had resulted in lower acceptability of these samples.

Figure 2. Influence of additions on color of gingerbreads: a) control sample, b) 3% sugar beet fibers and c) 10% carob flour.

However, the results also indicate that the optimization of biscuit formulation by choosing a correct amount of carob flour and sugar beet fibers in combination can lead to achieving improvement in both functional and sensory characteristics of gingerbread, while minimalizing the individual negative effects.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, usage of new functional materials in production of gingerbread type biscuits can be successfully implemented. Carob flour has proven to be a raw material rich in polyphenols, therefore can improve the functionality of final product increasing its total polyphenolic content and antioxidant activity. Even though, introduction of carob flour in gingerbread formulation changes typical sensory characteristics of biscuits, those changes are perceived as improvements. Moreover, due to high sugar content in carob flour and its ability to improve sweetness in biscuits, future studies should be focused on a possibility for reduction of sugar addition in gingerbread formulation for obtaining similar taste and sweetness. Sugar beet fibers introduced in the production of gingerbread type biscuits did not improve the functionality of products in terms of total polyphenolic content or antioxidant activity. On the other hand, value of enrichment of gingerbreads with sugar beet fibers lays in their possibility to increase the content of dietary fiber, which needs to be further investigated. Addition of sugar beet fibers in gingerbreads does not affect the appearance of biscuits, but has negative influence on taste and firmness of the product. However, those negative effects can be neglected by optimization of the formula for gingerbread type biscuits production.

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REFERENCES

- Ayaz, F. A., Torun, H., Ayaz, S., Correia, P. J., Alaiz, M., Sanz, C., Gruz, J., & Strnad, M. (2007). Determination of chemical composition of Anatolian carob pod (*Ceratonia siliqua* L.: sugars, aminoand organic acids, minerals and phenolic compounds. *Journal of Food Quality*, 30 (6), 1040-1055.
- Dinand, E., Chanzy, H., Vignon, R. M. (1999). Suspensions of cellulose microfibrils from sugar beet pulp. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 13 (3), 275-283.

- Filipčev, B., Šimurina, O., Sakač, M., Sedej, I., Jovanov, P., Pestorić, M., & Bodroža-Solarov, M. (2011). Feasibility of use of buckwheat flour as an ingredient in ginger nut biscuit formulation. *Food Chemistry*, 125, 164-170.
- Granato, D., Santos, J. S., Maciel, L. G., & Nunes, D. S. (2016). Chemical perspective and criticism on selected analytical methods used to estimate the total content of phenolic compounds in food matrices. *Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 80, 266-279.
- Haber, B. (2002). Carob fiber benefits and applications. *Cereal Foods World*, 47 (8), 365-369.
- International Organization for Standardization (ISO) (1987). Microbiology – General guidance for enumeration of yeasts and moulds – Colony count technique at 25 degrees C. Geneva, Switzerland.
- International Organization for Standardization (ISO) (2013). ISO 4833-1, Microbiology of the food chain – Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms – Part 1: Colony count at 30 degrees C by the pour plate technique. Geneva, Switzerland.
- Kitchevsky, D. (2001). Dietary fibre in health and disease. In B. V. McLeary & L. Prosky (Eds.), *Advanced dietary fibre technology*, pp. 149-161. Oxford, UK: Blackwell Science.
- Owen, R. W., Haubner, R., Hull, W. E., Erben, G., Spiegelhalder, B., Bartsch, H., & Haber, B. (2003). Isolation and structure elucidation of the major individual polyphenols in carob fibre. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 41 (12), 1727-1738.
- Pravilnik o metodama uzimanja uzoraka i metodama vršenja hemijskih i fizičkih analiza kako-zrna, kako-proizvoda, proizvoda sličnih čokoladi, bombonskih proizvoda, krem-proizvoda, keksa i proizvoda srodnih keksu (1987). *Službeni list SFRJ*, 41/87.
- Resurrecion, A. V. A. (2008). Consumer sensory testing for food product development. In A. L. Brody & J. B. Lord (Eds.), *Developing new products for a changing marketplace*, pp. 5-25. FL, USA: CRC Press Taylor and Francis Group.
- Sakač, M. B., Gyura, J. F., Mišan, A. Č., Šereš, Z. I., Pajin, B. S., & Šoronja-Simović, D. M. (2011). Antioxidant activity of cookies supplemented with sugarbeet dietary fiber. *Sugar Industry*, 136 (3), 151-157.
- Saura-Calixto, F. (1988). Effect of condensed tannins in the analysis of dietary fiber in carob pods. *Journal of Food Science*, 53 (6), 1769-1771.
- Šoronja-Simović, D., Filipović, N., Šereš, Z., Gyura, J., Jokić, A., & Pajin, B. (2010). Optimization of the formula of bread enriched with sugar beet fibers. *Acta Alimentaria*, 39 (4), 481-490.
- Šoronja-Simović, D., Šereš, Z., Maravić, N., Djordjević, M., Djordjević, M., Luković, J., & Tepić, A. (2016). Enhancement of physicochemical properties of sugar beet fibres affected by chemical modification and vacuum drying. *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, 100, 432-439.
- Zielinski, H., Dolores del Castillo, M., Przygodzka, M., Ciesarova, Z., Kukurova, K., & Zielinska, D. (2012). Changes in chemical composition and antioxidative properties of rye ginger cakes during their shelf-life. *Food Chemistry*, 135, 2965-2973.